

gall or other damage; locality and date of collection.

Specimens may be preserved by collecting into tubes of 70-80% alcohol. Movement of specimens within the tubes should be limited by inserting

small pieces of polythene film or tissue paper (*not* cotton-wool as it catches on claws and spines). Examination of representative series easily acquired from laboratory cultures will provide a check on culture identity.

Collections should be sent by air or sea mail (*not* air freight) to:

K. M. Harris, Commonwealth Institute of Entomology, c/o British Museum (Natural History), Cromwell Road, London SW7 SBD, UK. ■

Yellow stem borer damage to rice varieties in the Punjab, India

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Activity of the yellow stem borer *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker), a pest of tall basmati type varieties in the

Punjab, was suppressed with the introduction of high-yielding dwarf varieties. But recently serious infestations have appeared in localized pockets, particularly in Ferozepur district.

Five promising rice varieties were grown in 500 m² plots at different sites as farmers' field trials. PR106 and PR107 are high-yielding dwarf varieties; IET4141 is resistant to bacterial leaf

blight and sheath rot; Basmati 370 is a traditional tall, scented variety, and Bauni Basmati is a fine-grained, scented dwarf variety.

Incidence of deadhearts and whiteheads from 20 random hills was recorded 60-70 days after transplanting and 10-15 days before harvest. Damage to Basmati 370 was most severe (see table). ■

Incidence of yellow stem borer on rice varieties at different sites in the Punjab, India, 1981 kharif.^a

Variety	Cross	Duration (days)	Deadhearts (%)					Whiteheads (%)				
			Sodhi Nagar	Hamad	Bajeke	Mamdot	Av	Sodhi Nagar	Hamad	Bajeke	Jhoke Harihar	Av
Basmati 370	Pure line selection	145-155	32.4	15.2	NP	16.0	21.2	9.6	46.0	NP	NP	27.8
Bauni Basmati	Sona/Basmati 370	145-155	28.0	9.5	NP	9.1	15.7	5.8	32.4	NP	NP	19.0
IET4141	IR8/BJI//IR22	145-155	28.0	NP	1.24	NP	14.0	8.7	NP	10.6	7.4	8.9
PR107	Jaya/Palman 579	140-145	4.9	1.1	0.67	1.3	2.0	1.9	16.8	3.2	1.1	5.8
PR106	IR8//Peta ⁵ /Belle Patna	140-145	1.7	0.3	0.00	0.7	0.7	2.9	3.8	9.3	4.0	6.1

^a NP = variety not planted at the site.

Resistance of IR varieties to insect pests

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Rice varieties IR5 to IR54 were evaluated for resistance to hoppers, leaf-folder, and caseworm in greenhouse tests; striped and yellow stem borer in

the screenhouse; and whorl maggot in the field. Damage ratings were based on the Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

All IR varieties except IR22 showed resistance to at least one insect (see table). Although none of the varieties are resistant to the zigzag leafhopper and leaf folder, resistant donors have been identified and are being utilized in breeding programs. ■

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Resistance of IR varieties to insect pests,^a IRRI, 1981.

Variety	Brown planthopper			Green leaf hopper	White backed plant-hopper	Zigzag leaf-hopper	Yellow stem borer	Striped stem borer	Leaf-folder	Case-worm	Whorl maggot
	Biotype 1	Biotype 2	Biotype 3								
IR5	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR8	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR20	S	S	S	MR ^d	S	S	MR	R	S	S	S
IR22	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR24	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR26	R	S	R	MR	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S
IR28	R	S	R	R	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR29	R	S	R	R	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR30	R	S	R	R	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S
IR32	R	R	MR ^c	MR	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S

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Variety	Brown planthopper			Green leaf-hopper	White-backed plant-hopper	Zigzag leaf-hopper	Yellow stem borer	Striped stem borer	Leaf-folder	Case-worm	Whorl maggot
	Biotype 1	Biotype 2	Biotype 3								
IR34	R	S	R	R	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S
IR36	R	R	MR ^c	MR	S	S	MR	R	S	S	S
IR38	R	R	MR ^c	MR	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S
IR40	R	MR	S	MR	S	S	MR	R	S	S	MR
IR42	R	R	S	MR ^d	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S
IR43	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S	MR	S	S	S
IR44	R	R	MR ^c	MR	S	S	S	R	S	S	S
IR45	R	S	R	MR	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR46	R	S ^b	R	MR ^d	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR48	R	R	S	MR	MR	S	S	S	S	S	S
IR50	R	R	MR ^c	R	S	S	MR	R	S	S	S
IR52	R	R	MR ^c	R	MR	S	S	MR	S	S	S
IR54	R	R	S	R	S	S	MR	MR	S	S	S

^aReplicated experiments. Hopper resistance based on greenhouse evaluation of seedlings; yellow and striped stem borer resistance based on screenhouse evaluation of 40- to 70-day-old plants; leaf folder and caseworm resistance based on the reaction of 30- and 11-day-old plants in the greenhouse; whorl maggot resistance based on field observations at 30 days after transplanting. Ratings, based on Standard Evaluation System for Rice: 1-3 = resistant (R), 5-7 = moderately resistant (MR), and 9 = susceptible (S). ^bIR46 has field resistance to biotype 2. ^cReactions to biotype 3 vary, occasionally susceptible and often resistant. ^dOccasional susceptible reactions.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Deep water

Vegetative regeneration in floating rice

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Two types of cuttings and two planting methods were used to study vegetative regeneration for retrieval of floating rice plants. Healthy stems were cut into sets, with two open nodes in top cuttings and two to three nodes in mid-stem cuttings. Cuttings were planted both vertically

and horizontally.

Top cuttings (48) with just-sprouting and developed aquatic roots were planted in submerged soil (20 cm water) 10 cm apart in vertical planting, and end-to-end in horizontal planting with 20 cm interrow spacing. Unsprouted mid-stem cuttings (48) were inserted straight in vertical planting and planted in furrows in horizontal planting.

In top cuttings, dormant buds sprouted on day 5 and tillers were seen after 1 week. In horizontal planting, the

middle bud sprouted at a 75-98° angle.

In vertical planting, shoots emerged from the lower and middle buds parallel to the cutting.

Sets were transplanted 1 week after emergence and waterlogging was maintained. Performance of the regenerated plants was compared with that of normal plants (see table).

Survival was highest with vertical planting. Yield characteristics were very low, but might be improved by adjusting planting time. ■

Performance of floating rice stem cuttings and normal plants at Ghaghraghat, India.

Treatment	Survival (%)	Plant height (cm)	Tillers/plant (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Grains/panicle (no.)	Sterility (%)	Flag leaf area (cm ²)	100-grain weight (g)	Yield per Plant (g)
Stem - top cuttings, developed roots, planted vertically	82.5	94.0	8.6	22.6	118	18.1	12.7	2.2	4.0
Stem - top cuttings, developed roots, planted horizontally	79.1	91.1	6.8	21.5	107	20.4	19.1	2.2	3.4
Stem - top cuttings, sprouted roots, planted vertically	79.1	93.8	6.4	21.3	99	19.8	16.5	2.2	3.3
Stem - top cuttings, sprouted roots, planted horizontally	82.5	86.7	4.0	22.5	105	20.5	16.6	2.2	3.5
Mid-stems planted vertically	73.7	83.3	6.3	19.3	105	25.4	17.6	2.1	2.7
Mid-stems planted horizontally	58.8	90.6	5.6	22.2	104	25.6	15.3	2.1	2.0
Normal plant	-	425.0	10.4	27.4	154	15.3	24.1	2.5	28.6